

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

Guidelines on the content and use of the tools

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MATILDE has received
funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation
programme under grant
agreement No 870831

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MATILDE toolbox for self-
assessment for practitioners
and policy makers:

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Call: H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Work Programmes:

H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth

H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change.

Deliverable 6.7 - MATILDE toolbox for self-assessment for practitioners and policy makers: Guidelines on the content and use of the tools

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Proofreading: Rupert Moreton

Version: 25.11.2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7371898

How to cite: Gruber, M./Pöcher, J./Zupan, K. (2022): MATILDE toolbox for self-assessment for practitioners and policy makers: Guidelines on the content and use of the tools. MATILDE Deliverable 6.7. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7371898.

The individual guidelines are available online: <https://matilde-migration.eu/toolbox/>.

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 870831 for the European Commission. It does not necessary reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

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Introduction

MATILDE applies a mixed-method approach of quantitative (descriptive and interpretative statistics), qualitative (e.g. interviews), and participatory action research methods in cooperation between researchers and practitioners to assess the social and economic impact of third-country nationals. This transdisciplinary setting of researchers and practitioners in MATILDE aims to involve stakeholders actively, based on cooperation and equality. A common basis of methods and tools is therefore required – further developed and adapted to local needs (Gruber et al. 2020). First, the “MATILDE toolbox: methods to assess migration impact in rural and mountain areas” (Kordel et al. 2022) was developed as a common set of methods for data collection and analysis. Second, a toolbox for policymakers and administrative staff and stakeholders in NGOs or public services at all governmental levels from the local to EU level was created. In line with the MATILDE Grant Agreement (2019) the MATILDE toolbox for policymakers aims to support the assessment of the status quo of integration work and policies to enable possible improvements. For this purpose, existing tools, collected e.g. in Kordel et al. 2022 or Gruber 2013, were adapted and further developed for easy application by policymakers and practitioners to obtain an overview of the status quo at local and regional level and to monitor existing measures at national and EU level. Guidelines on how to use each tool were therefore developed and will be presented in the report below. Further details and information about the documentation, possibilities of upscaling, level of participation and citizen activation, and standardization can be found in the ‘Self-assessment Toolbox for Practitioners and Policymakers’ (Gruber et al. 2022).

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Tool 1: Municipality

Profile

Definition and Application

The municipality profile is intended to help municipalities gain an **overview of the current and future situation** via quantitative and qualitative assessment regarding various topics like:

- the current and future demographic situation
- the peculiarities of the municipality
- the economic and labour market situation
- the educational background of the population
- infrastructure, including education and healthcare facilities or public spaces
- the budgetary situation
- the social climate in the municipality

It can assist comparisons with other municipalities and help approach the topic of integration. A **standardized template is provided** to help municipalities answer the open questions. Various people should therefore work on filling in the template.

Preparation:

Clarify the following questions:

1. What **information is already available**, and what information needs to be requested for the creation of the municipality profile, to collect all the relevant information from different departments and stakeholders? (Gruber 2013; Stadt Wien 2020).
2. Which **participants should be invited for the development process** of the municipality profile to increase perspectives on the topic and include the views of different target groups? (Gruber 2013).

Conducting

1. Agree on a **moderator**, e.g. from the public administration in the municipality.
2. **Explain why a municipality profile is being created**, and what will happen with the collected information.
3. **Define aims**, e.g. to obtain an up-to-date overview of the municipality's current situation, assess impacts of migration on different areas of life, foster the exchange with stakeholders and citizens, or use the results to draft policy recommendations and measures for improvement.
4. **Present the already available statistical information.**
5. **Discuss open questions** on missing information from the template, which can expose needs, e.g. in the design of a focus group (see also Kordel et. al. 2022, chapter 3.2)
6. **Document statistical data and discussion results** in the template.

However, the municipality profile cannot only be created for municipalities but for multiple entities at different governance levels such as districts, provinces, or states. The group of participants must then be adapted for each entity.

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Tool 2: Photo/Video Talk

Definition and Application

Photo or video talks can be designed for various purposes, target groups, and with a varying degree of participation (Kordel et al. 2022) to facilitate discussions of problems. The aim is to gain an impression of the participant's living environment. There are three different approaches:

- **Photo elicitation:** photographic material of a specific topic (selected by the interviewer) is discussed and reviewed with participants
- **Photo novella:** pictures/videos are taken by the participants to document their life and perspective over a longer period
- **Reflexive photography:** pictures/videos are taken by the participants and jointly reflected on to understand the thought processes involved in creating the material.

Preparation:

In preparing to use this tool, it is necessary to decide which approach will be used. Based on this, it is important to:

- Communicate to the participants exactly what is expected of them (introductory meeting with all participants)
- Clarify the equality of participants independent of experience and perspective
- Decide if private devices will be used, or if disposable cameras are provided.

Conducting:

Example: A municipality would like to improve the integration of former asylum seekers who have settled in the area, as there are often conflicts with the other residents, who complain that they keep to themselves and stay mostly in certain parts of the area.

1. **Contact potential participants** (locals and former asylum seekers) and make an agreement to take week-long photographs of their daily lives.
2. Receive pictures taken by the participants and print them before the discussion date.
3. Invite participants to the group and provide a room and catering for a comfortable atmosphere.
4. As a possible introduction, ask the participants how they liked taking the photos/videos.
5. Use a **picture/video to start the actual discussion**. Based on the pictures, participants talk about their daily lives, problems, and needs.
6. Use pictures as an **intervention** to enable different perspectives on certain problems.
7. Retain **freedom in the choice of material** discussed.
8. If necessary, engage the participants in refocusing on the picture material.
9. Find a joint agreement in a final discussion – for example, for greater need for more inclusive housing.

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Tool 3: Investigation of areas of action

Definition and application:

The investigation of areas of action is an analysis that combines the examination of the current situation in a specific (political) field with a **SWOT Analysis** (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) to obtain an overview of the fields where action is needed. The assessment is not limited to certain institutions or groups or related to the field of integration (e.g. it can also be applied in the field of rural development) (Gruber 2013).

Preparation:

The analysis can be standardized with the aid of template observation sheets. These templates contain exemplary questions that give an idea of what could be analysed in the respective field of action. However, the questions allow for a more in-depth analysis and can be adapted and expanded. Prepare these observation sheets in cooperation with the

participants and roughly determine which places should be visited. This requires a preparatory meeting so that the participants get to know each other in advance, and the onsite visit can start working on the content immediately. The selection and composition of the participants is crucial. A moderator/coordinator must be provided by the coordination team.

Conducting:

1. The area of action investigation starts with an **onsite visit** to locations and facilities in the respective field of action. For example, if the ‘housing’ action area is to be analysed, housing complexes, private apartment buildings, housing estates, and the outdoor facilities of residential buildings are to be visited, e.g. with a view of playgrounds, public parks, and meeting places without compulsion to consume, the accessibility of the housing complexes by public transport, and the proximity of childcare facilities and educational institutions.
2. Conduct the inspection tour **with different stakeholders**.
3. Use the ‘structured participatory observation’ method (more details in Kordel et al. 2022, chapter 3.4) for the onsite visit. The prepared observation form allows notes to be made about the respective observation point (e.g. residential facilities, presence of infrastructure, places of intercultural encounter). Encourage the participants of the observation **to take pictures for better documentation** during the onsite visit. When access to the field of interest is completed, the stakeholders start to take notes about their impressions. The assessment is carried out in several phases as described by Kordel et al. (2022).
4. Make sure the participants only concentrate on those observations which fit the defined areas of interest well. In the given example of housing this could be the composition of residents in neighbourhoods or housing estates. Pause briefly together to discuss the initial findings and decide what the focus of a more in-depth observation should be. After the second phase a third observation phase can still be carried out, in which specific places of interest are selected and visited.

5. Carry out a parallel statistical inventory, coordinated by an official of the municipal office, for example (or another institution with the largest overview of the existing data). In the field of housing this statistical inventory should include data on the number of public and cooperative housing units, private rented flats and houses, the number of refugee shelters, housing applicants on the waiting list for subsidized housing, etc.
6. Under the guidance of the facilitator/coordinator, the group of stakeholders meets in a roundtable and first identifies changes and impacts in the study area based on the results.
7. Second, conduct a SWOT analysis with the observation group. In this step the results of the roundtable (instructions for conducting a roundtable, see MATILDE toolbox for self-assessment for Practitioners and Policymakers, from p. 47) are brought together and enriched with the participants' further background and expert knowledge. The result is a SWOT and impact analysis for the respective field of action, which provides a structured overview. Subsequently, the area in which action is needed is jointly determined.

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Tool 4: Future Forum

Definition and application:

Although the Future Forum is resource-intensive, it imbeds the **potential for learning and sustainable change** (Vetter and Remer-Bollow 2016). The aim of the standardized process is to **openly express wishes and criticisms, develop well-founded alternative courses of action** to existing problems, and **empower participants** to effectively represent these proposed solutions to third parties. Nevertheless, they can be adapted to the individual needs.

Preparation:

1. Choose a **moderator**, who is preferably an external person with experience of change processes.
2. Choose an external person for the **documentation** (of content and observations) of the whole process (Albers 2001).
3. Identify, select, and involve **participants** representing all the affected areas.

4. Invite participants early enough (Future Forums usually last 2–3 days but can be shortened to 1–1.5 days). It is especially important to identify and request experts early enough.

Conducting:

Example: with the support of didactical techniques, the Future Forum includes five phases (including the preliminary phase and follow-up) (Koch 1999) which will be explained with the aid of an example of where a city aims to invest in public transport for equal access for all population groups and increased sustainability.

Preliminary Phase

1. Invite citizens from all parts of the city to jointly develop a mobility concept.
2. Introduce each other.
3. Explain the time schedule and the main topics.

1st phase – complaints and criticism

4. All participants express anger about public transportation connections.
5. Participants may experience similar critical points.
6. Recognize that some citizens are excluded from the public transport network.

2nd phase – fantasy and utopia

7. Collect and discuss ideas and creative solutions with the aid of brainstorming techniques – e.g. discuss a separate shuttle service for pupils in the excluded areas.

3rd phase – realization and practice

8. Present ideas to experts, e.g. in city planning.
9. Develop concrete approaches with their help, e.g. redesign the bus routes throughout the city to reach more pupils.

Follow-up

10. Decide how to proceed and the immediate steps to be taken.
11. Close the Future Forum.

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Tool 5: Focus Groups

Definition and application:

Focus groups represent a form of **group discussion on a specific topic**, and the relevant information is collected through group interaction. Focus groups can be used to explore a topic or to validate findings and solutions from diverse perspectives (Kordel et al. 2022). The fields of application are wide-ranging, and the lifeworlds of the participants, their attitudes to a topic, their experiences, everyday routines, and challenges and solution strategies on diverse topics like ‘intercultural housing’, ‘multilingualism’, ‘labour market integration’, or ‘racism and discrimination’ can therefore be discussed.

Preparation:

Kordel et al. (2022) recommend the following steps for preparation:

- **Participants and moderation:** Avoid inviting participants with an imbalance of power so that all participants can speak freely about the topic at hand. The number of participants can vary. Depending on the topic, 4-12 people may be a good number.

The focus group is led by a moderator (for more details see Kordel et al. 2022, p. 22) who is not directly involved in the topic and has no vested interests.

- **Locality: Choose** a place that is accessible to all participants and quiet, without symbolic meaning that could be exclusionary or cause rejection among some participants (e.g. religious buildings) to ensure a pleasant discussion atmosphere.
- **Duration:** Depending on the type of topic and the objectives, the focus group's duration can also vary. It can last up to 5.5 hours.

Conducting:

Example: The following steps (for more details see Kordel et al. 2022) are described based on the area of action 'economy and employment': a higher proportion of older people who have already retired lives in the 'Abandoned land' region. The young generation commutes to other regions to take better paid jobs or to study in another city. It is noticeable that many jobs in the care sector and in tourism cannot be filled. However, many younger migrants have come to the region. They are looking for jobs but are usually not invited to job interviews. The focus group involving migrants and regional employers aims to find out the challenges migrants face in finding a job and how to solve the mismatch on the labour market.

1. **Introduction:** Welcome the participants and introduce your own person and role, as well as the focus group's aims. Additionally, present sponsors, data protection rules, and rules for discussion.
2. **First-Person Perspective ('I'):** Invite the participants to present themselves.
3. **Group Perspective ('We'):** Collect the participants' experiences, perspectives, and positions in relation to the topic, including their professional/practical background.
4. **Main Questions/Issues ('It'):** In the focus group discussion migrants mainly bring the perspective that captures the challenges to entering the labour market, while employers bring the perspective of the barriers for employing migrants. The participants also discuss measures to address the mismatch in the labour market.

5. **Conclusions:** Summarize the results of the discussion and give the participants the opportunity to contribute opposing views to those presented or to add further important aspects.

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Tool 6: Roundtables

Definition and application:

The roundtable is an organizational approach involving a round of discussions with participants sitting around a round table – to express equality. It aims to **discuss solutions to complex and conflictual topics**. The discussion is intended to be open-ended, without a determined outcome or only one possible solution. Representatives with diverse perspectives on the discussion topics participate. Possible topics are the development of a concept for sustainable urban development, a marketing strategy for a region, recommendations for improved migrant integration, or actions to prevent violence. Of course, conflicts should be tackled, and different views and opinions accepted (Wüst 2018).

Preparation:

Following Wüst (2018), the followings steps should be considered in the preparation phase:

1. Explore relevant actors, topics, and issues.
2. Invite participants.
3. Choose a moderator who is neither participant nor affected by the discussed problem, and who is accepted by all participants.

4. Choose an attractive, spacious, and easily accessible location.
5. Offer drinks and small snacks (as it may last up to four hours).

Conducting:

Example: The following conducting procedure for a roundtable is based on the general procedure for roundtables (see Wüst 2018), as well as the ‘focus groups’ method (see Kordel et al. 2022). It will be explained by an example of intercultural housing because problems in the integration policy field of housing often exist in (rural) municipalities.

1. **Call for a roundtable.**
2. **Invite representatives** from the public administration, housing cooperatives, property management, neighbourhood supervisors, and residents with and without a migrant background living in conflict areas.
3. **Define the aims** of the roundtable, e.g. explore the most important problems concerning intercultural housing and living together, define measures that can help avoid those problems or solve them, and/or agree which steps must be taken and by whom.
4. **Introduce the role of the moderator and the aims** of the roundtable.
5. **Define the rules** for discussion.
6. **Increase transparency** about cooperation and exchange of information between the roundtable, politics, and administration, including information about the effects of the results.
7. **Introduce the participants** and their position in relation to the topic.
8. **Get an overview** of the respective problems.
9. **Collect and develop possible solutions and measures jointly** to meet the problems in intercultural housing.
10. **Prioritize the interventions** by using evaluation methods.
11. **Decide** on the interventions which should be implemented.
12. Organize a **feedback loop** about the interventions with an extended group of interested parties (onionskin principle; Arbter 2018).

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Tool 7: Open Space

Definition and application:

Open Spaces can be conducted to **discuss opportunities and challenges in several complex topics and problems in a municipality**. The discussions are more fruitful when diverse people and innovative and productive tools are linked. Open Spaces differs from the focus groups and roundtables in that it is more open: everyone who is interested can participate, and the participants suggest and decide the topics for discussion. The outcome should be binding to influence change and development processes (Kordel et al. 2022).

Preparation:

Decide a topic with an **initial question**, e.g. how can the social integration of newcomers be improved? How can public transport be developed to reach more people living in the municipality?

1. **Invite people** who are interested in the selected topic to join voluntarily; e.g. representatives from civil society, public administrations, associations, NGOs, etc.
2. **Organize a location** for 1–3 days with a sitting circle and a free wall (Owen 2001).

Conducting:

Example: The Open Space tool (Owen 2001) will be explained with the aid of an example of more respectful communication by the local population with newcomers.

1. **Welcome** and introduce the participants.
2. Explain the **discussion aim**, e.g. to increase respectful communication.
3. Ask the participants to **note ideas and worries** about respectful communication on a bulletin board.
4. Invite the participants to **choose one of the collected topics** afterwards.
5. **Discuss ideas and solutions** about the chosen topic with people who have chosen the same topic.
6. Document the discussed topics, responsible persons, and discussion participants.
7. Change the discussion group by the 'law of two feet' (Owen 2001).
8. **Rank the most important topics** based on the notes of all the discussion rounds.
9. Pool and **decide the implementation** of solutions, e.g. introductory evenings and a regular get-together might be solutions for improved communication with newcomers.

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Tool 8: Mobility Map

Definition and application:

The mobility map is recommended for local communities to address challenges and improvement needs for the region, e.g. regarding the (im)mobility situation of the population. 'Mobility mapping is a spatio-visual tool, which allows to investigate the spatial dimension of everyday life of individuals or groups, and to quantitatively and qualitatively capture both spatial (im)mobility and the meanings attached to places' (Kordel et al. 2022, p. 41).

Preparation:

- **Participants and conductors:** A mobility map is drawn by a single person or a family, depending on the theme or regional issue chosen by the local community. For the implementation of a mobility map, it is necessary to define the roles and responsibilities in advance.
- **Locality:** Choose an appropriate location featuring a big table or enough space on the floor.

- **Work material:** Prepare work material such as small cards of different shapes for the places frequented (or not) with pictograms about different realms of everyday life; different coloured marker pens for the different modes of transport and prompt cards with the respective pictograms and short written explanations; the latter should be provided in all relevant languages spoken by the participants; the material should be standardized to foster intersubjective traceability (Kordel et al. 2022).

Conducting:

Example: The local community found people with disabilities tended to focus on one area according to their daily life activities. For the Mobility Map, people with different physical disabilities are invited. In this case it may be necessary to adapt the various phases of the process to be accessible to the disabled.

1. **Explain the purpose**, e.g. that the local community is interested in learning about the everyday life and (im)mobility practices of people with physical disabilities. In addition, explain how the method works. Invite the participants **to draw their apartment, house, or accommodation** in the centre of the poster and ask them **to talk about the places they usually visit** in their everyday lives.
2. **Encourage** those who hesitate to draw and write by themselves while offering assistance throughout the process, e.g. in providing the ‘correct’ spelling of the place. Do not interrupt once **the participants have started to narrate or write/draw on the small cards** until they stop.
3. After they have finished, ask the participants to **clarify or add places they had mentioned but had not written/drawn, or vice versa**.
4. Let the **participants arrange the small cards with the places visited around the apartment/house/accommodation** according to the perceived distance from their home. If the participant is happy with the arrangement, the small cards are glued onto the poster.

5. Afterwards invite the participants **to draw lines between the house and the places visited**, indicating the means of transport used to reach these places. Different coloured marker pens are used for different methods of transport.
6. If they had not yet done so before, encourage the participant to **explain the meaning of the places they have drawn**.
7. Then ask **the participants to draw or write the names of places where they have to go to but do not want to, as well as places they never frequent** for various reasons, on differently shaped small cards.
8. Finally, fix the **cards on the poster** and take a picture of the final version of the map and give the map to the participant.

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Tool 9: Social Map

Definition and application:

A social map is a tool for exploring the spatial dimensions of people's realities. Local communities can thus find out how their residents perceive their living environment, their relationships within the local community, and their access to resources. The practical implementation of the social map is designed so that the participants draw a map and express their thoughts aloud during this (Kordel et al. 2022).

Preparation:

- **Participants and conductors:** A social map can be implemented with both individuals and groups. If groups are chosen, one effective way is to ask the group to nominate a person to draw the map. The number of social maps to be drawn depends on the topic and the size of the community. Two facilitators are needed: a moderator and a notetaker. In previous projects, social maps have taken between 1.5 and 2 hours to prepare well.
- **Location:** The chosen location must be a central place accessible to all members of society and offering a good working atmosphere.

- **Work material:** Provide adequate work material such as posters for drawing, pens in different colours, pictogram cards, etc. (Kordel et al. 2022).

Conducting:

Example: In a fictitious small rural municipality, a group of refugees have arrived, and policymakers want to know how they perceive the new locality compared with the local people. The social map is used to filter out the social relations in the village. A social map is therefore elaborated with a group of refugees and local people. The participants are divided into these groups to prepare a social map. In this case it may be necessary to be alert for any tension between the participants and intervene promptly.

1. **Explain the purpose of the tool** to all the participants and include a brief description of what is expected of them. Before beginning, each group nominates one participant for the drawing ('illustrator').
2. First, ask the participants **to draw the main physical features of their locality and their social relations**, e.g. where they live. The illustrator therefore draws what the other participants in their group contribute during the discussion.
3. Keep watching and listening to the discussions and the drawing process attentively. Meanwhile, **the notetaker takes detailed notes**.
4. **Let the discussion flow** and show faith in the participants. They should have total control and initiative.
5. Keep an eye on the participation of every perspective **and take proactive steps to involve those being left out**.
6. **Only intervene when necessary**, e.g. when interaction between the participants is tense.
7. Suggest clarifications or additions gently, e.g. by asking 'What about...?'. The mapping is complete **when nothing more is added by the participants** (Kordel et al. 2022).

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Tool 10: Village Talk

Definition and application:

The village talk was developed with the aim to produce open and diverse societies (Wenzel and Boeser-Schnebel 2019a). **Personal, emotional, and value-based dialogues** with a focus on values, similarities, and differences are key. Existing hierarchies and structures need to be overcome to share participation, responsibility, and joint action with stakeholders and representatives from diverse organizations, policymakers, and civil society, especially in the implementation of the results (ibid. 2019a; ibid. 2019b; Kordel et al. 2022). It is an upgrade to Open Space, with a more in-depth analysis of the stakeholders beforehand and more standardized conduct, with a concrete aim for each dialogue evening.

Preparation:

The village talk process lasts 6–9 months without the implementation process (Wenzel and Boeser-Schnebel 2019a).

1. A **core team** of 2–4 ‘door-openers’ and ‘bridgebuilders’ (ibid., 42) looks for interested people and reflects on motivation and values.
2. Start the **stakeholder process**, which is 80% of the duration.

3. **Spread and explain the information** about the village talk among the municipality's population.
4. **Categorize the stakeholders** according to their position in the municipality, their relations, conflicts, and power structure (done by core team).
5. Interview the stakeholders to obtain information about their **motivation, potentials, and doubts**.
6. Rank the stakeholders and **select 10–20 stakeholders** to organize the village talk, reflect on their position in the municipality and in the village talk, and invite people to participate.
7. Create a **flyer or website** to further distribute the information about the village talk.

Conducting:

The village talk is conducted in three dialogue evenings (each of 3 hours' duration) focusing on **'civil relationships, deliberation, and collaboration'** (Wenzel and Boeser-Schnebel 2019a, 68) to exchange and discuss issues via various methods. Each step of the process is documented by notes (from interviews, discussions, worksheets), reflection sheets, photos/videos, or results on flipcharts.

1st dialogue evening – 'civil relationships'

1. Focus on the diversity of motivations, talents, potential, and resources in the municipality, e.g. people are asked to mark their position in the village in a circle, and how people from more outside can be better involved.
2. Discuss and reflect on the motivation for participation, the highlights, liveability, development, and vision of the municipality.

2nd dialogue evening – 'deliberation'

3. Focus on differences and conflicts, their diversity, and the tension of values.
4. Discuss the three main challenges of the municipality, the fields of tension and values, and who can take responsibility for changes in small groups.

3rd dialogue evening – 'collaboration'

5. Discuss necessary changes for the municipality.

6. Formulate topics positively and create solutions or ideas for how to deal with them.
7. Discuss how the solutions/ideas can be implemented (by stakeholders).
8. Organize active working groups and request support.

‘Follow-up, evaluation, and implementation’

9. Invite the stakeholders, participants, and other people again.
10. Evaluate the improvements resulting from the village talk.

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